

Strength Behaviour of Lime treated Channarayapatna soil reinforced with Coir Fiber

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Abstract : Channarayapatna Soil is a Brownish red Soil by appearance Softy Clayey structure which is having natural moisture holding capacity higher than natural soil however as the plastic limit is higher this soil behaves like a low plastic soil with high rate of Permeability hence even though it comes under clay of intermediate compressibility an attempt is done to enhance the strength and ductility behavior of this soil by adding lime as a stabilizing material and by conducting Triaxial shear strength test under 50Kpa Cell pressure. Further as the plasticity index is low to accelerate the ductility behavior of that soil randomly distributed coir fiber will be added to lime treated soil. From Triaxial shear strength test it has been found that for all curing periods Channarayapatna Soil treated with 2% lime enhances the highest strength when compared with all other curing periods and hence it is found to be optimum. Further to that treated soil 0.5% randomly distributed coir fiber both untreated and NaCl treated are added in its Isolation condition. It has been found that NaCl treated fiber performance better than untreated Coir fiber and in order to reduce the permeability of that soil this matrix testing was also extended to permeability test and it is found that presence of lime permeability reduces. However, addition of coir fiber in lime stabilized soil marginally increases permeability on compare to lime treated soil. This indicates addition of fiber originally increases the Permeability but not up to the extent of soil alone. Hence it is beneficial to Civil Engineering stabilization technique.

Index Terms - Stabilization, Matrix, Treated fiber.

I. INTRODUCTION

India, with its diverse climate and geography, boasts a wide variety of soils. These soils are integral to the country's agricultural productivity and ecological balance. The main types of soils in India are alluvial, black, red, laterite, arid, forest, and saline-alkaline soils.

1.Alluvial Soil: Alluvial soil, found primarily in the river basins of the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and the Indus, covers about 40% of India's land area. This soil is highly fertile due to its rich mineral content and good water retention capacity. It is categorized into two types: old alluvium (bhangar) and new alluvium (khadar). Bhangar soils are found in slightly elevated areas and are coarser, while khadar soils are found in low-lying areas and are more fertile and finer. Alluvial soil is ideal for growing a variety of crops such as rice, wheat, sugarcane, and pulses.

2.Black Soil: Black soil, also known as regur soil, is predominant in the Deccan Plateau, covering states like Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat, and Andhra Pradesh. This soil is rich in clay and known for its moisture-retaining capacity, which makes it suitable for cotton cultivation, earning it the nickname "cotton soil." It also supports crops like sorghum, millets, tobacco, and oilseeds. Black soil is rich in lime, iron, magnesia, and alumina but lacks nitrogen, phosphorous, and organic matter.

3.Red Soil: Red soil is found in regions with a warm, temperate climate, such as Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, southern Maharashtra, Chhattisgarh, Odisha, and parts of Madhya Pradesh. Its characteristic red color is due to the presence of iron oxide. Red soil is generally shallow, poor in nitrogen, phosphorus, and humus but rich in potassium. Despite its low fertility, it can support crops like cotton, wheat, pulses, millets, and oilseeds with proper fertilization and irrigation.

4.Laterite Soil: Laterite soil, formed under high temperature and heavy rainfall conditions with alternating wet and dry periods, is found in the Western Ghats, eastern Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, and parts of Odisha. This soil is rich in iron and aluminum but poor in nitrogen, phosphorous, and lime. Laterite soils are suitable for crops like tea, coffee, rubber, coconut, and cashew nuts. Due to their leaching properties, they require significant fertilization for agriculture.

5.Arid Soil: Arid soil is found in the arid and semi-arid regions of Rajasthan, parts of Gujarat, Punjab, and Haryana. These soils are sandy, alkaline, and low in organic matter. They are characterized by high salt content and low fertility but can be made productive with proper irrigation and soil management practices. Crops like barley, millets, pulses, and cotton can be grown in arid soils with adequate water supply.

6. Forest Soil: Forest soil is found in the hilly and forested areas of Jammu and Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand, the Eastern and Western Ghats, and the northeastern states. These soils are rich in organic matter and humus due to the dense vegetation but vary in fertility depending on the location and altitude. They support the growth of diverse forest vegetation and crops like tea, coffee, spices, and tropical fruits.

7. Saline-Alkaline Soil: Saline-alkaline soils are found in arid and semi-arid regions, particularly in parts of Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, Haryana, Rajasthan, and Maharashtra. These soils are characterized by high salt content and pH, leading to poor fertility. They require extensive soil management techniques, such as gypsum application and proper drainage, to reduce salinity and alkalinity. Once reclaimed, they can support crops like rice, barley, and sugar beet.

Fig 1: Courtesy by <https://images.app.goo.gl/fTuM7wJEBrwMjLyE9>

II. Literature Review

Vishwas Nandikishor and Rakesh Kumar Dutta (2024) says in their experiment study on “**Shear Strength, Bearing Ratio and Settlement Behavior of Clay Reinforced with Chemically Treated Coir Fibers**” says that the effect of chemically treated coir fibers on shear strength, bearing ratio and settlement behavior of clay is presented in this study. The clay in the present study is reinforced with untreated, sodium hydroxide-treated and potassium permanganate-treated coir fibers. The shear strength behavior of unreinforced as well as reinforced clay is examined by conducting a series of unconfined compression strength, direct shear tests. Additionally, the load deformation and compressibility characteristics of unreinforced and reinforced soil are studied by performing bearing ratio and consolidation tests. The coir fiber content was varied from 0.25% to 1.5% (by weight) of soil. The results of unconfined compression strength tests on saturated and unsaturated clay indicated that the deviator stress at failure of clay and clay with untreated coir fibers can be increased by treatment with potassium permanganate and sodium hydroxide. The results of consolidation study showed a reduction in settlement at given load for soil reinforced with untreated/treated coir fibers.

Rithy Dompheon and Amin Eisazadeh (2024) says in their experiment study on “**Flexural and Shear Strength Properties of Laterite Soil Stabilized with Rice Husk Ash, Coir Fiber, and Lime.**” Says that the effects of Rice Husk Ash (RHA), Lime (L), and Coir Fiber (CF) as soil reinforcement material on the engineering properties of laterite soil. Several tests were conducted including the Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) test, three-point bending flexural strength, direct shear test, to observe the micro-structural changes of stabilized soil. The laterite soil was replaced by 10%, and 20% of RHA, 1% of CF, and 8% of L. The samples were cured for 7, 28, and 56 days before conducting the tests. The 20%RHA, 8%L mix designs showed the highest UCS value after 56 days curing period. In terms of the durability test results, the 20%RHA, 8%L mix design also exhibited the lowest reduction in compressive strength (3.8% drop) after undergoing 6 wetting- drying cycles. According to flexural strength, the 20% RHA, 1% CF, 8% L mix design indicated a tenfold increase in flexural strength compared to the natural laterite soil after 28 days of curing. Based on the findings of this research, CF and RHA are beneficial for earth structures such as embankments and road layers that are subjected to significant tensile stresses. These waste materials can also reduce the brittleness of lime-stabilized soil.

Nawaz Qureshi and Shilpa Indra Jain (2023) says in their experiment study on “Review on Stabilization of Soil Using Coconut Coir Fiber, Lime and Portland Slag Cement” says that Soil stabilization techniques are used to improve soil properties. With 0,0.5 1, 2, and 3% coconut coir fiber per mass of the black soil samples, the aim of this study is to assess the benefits of coconut coir fiber on the stabilization of low-strength soils. For achieving our research objectives, for this we have to perform the following laboratory tests on the black soil samples: California Bearing Ratio Test (CBR Test), Unconfined Compressive Strength Test (UCS Test), Optimum Moisture Content Test (OMC Test), Maximum Dry Density Test (MDD Test).

Anita et.al., (2023) says in their experiment study on “Combination of Coir Fiber Waste and Coir-Wood Ash for Expansive Clay Stabilization” says that combined coir fibers with a mixture of coir-wood ash, the waste from the tofu home industry. This study aims to examine the soaked and unsoaked California Bearing Ratio (CBR), swelling, unconfined compressive strength (UCS), and tensile strength of soil mixed with 0.75% fiber, and ash with varying content: 0%, 2%, 4%, 6%, 8%, and 10% of the mixture’s total weight. The curing time was seven days, 14 days, and 28 days. Testing refers to ASTM. The test results unveiled that the unsoaked CBR, soaked CBR, UCS, and tensile strength increased with rising ash content and curing time. A 6%–8% ash content produced the highest CBR, UCS, and tensile strength. On the other hand, by including a 6%–10% ash content, the swelling was decreased to 0%. Combining coir fibers and coir-wood ash has proven very effective for stabilizing expansive clays. In comparison to soils merely reinforced with fiber, the addition of coir-wood ash can eliminate swelling and increase the value of soaked CBR, UCS, tensile strength, and secant modulus up to 534%, 349%, 105%, and 824 %, respectively.

Boobalan and Sivakami Devi (2022) says in their experiment study on “Investigational Study on the Influence of Lime and Coir Fiber in the Stabilization of Expansive Soil” says that Coir fibers are rich in lignin content that helps them to retain their tensile strength even in wet condition. The effect of penetration level, compression and shearing were experimented for plain and reinforced soil with varying fiber content such as 0%, 0.5%, 1%, 1.5% along with 5% optimum lime addition based on the previous research studies. The results shows that CBR values increases beyond the 1.5% and UCS and Shear strength attains a maximum value at 1% addition of fiber and 5% optimum level of lime. Hence 1% coir fiber content and 5% lime is concluded to be the optimum addition for an effective soil stabilization.

III. Materials and Methods

3.1 Channarayapatna (CRP) Soil: Channarayapatna soil was collected from a Y. Singenahalli village agriculture field in open pit method at a depth of 0.5-0.6 m. this soil is brown clayey soil and it had also mixed with fine grains, some amount of pond clayey soil and red earth soil. Channarayapatna is a town in the Hassan district of Karnataka, India.

Table 1: Physical property of CRP Soil

SI No.	Content	Particulars
1	Colour	Brownish red
2	Texture	Soft clayey soil
3	Moisture content	31.62%
4	Specific gravity	2.45
5	Liquid Limit	36%
6	Plastic Limit	29%
7	Plasticity index	Low Plastic Clay
8	Shrinkage limit	26%
9	OMC	13.3%
10	MDD	22.1 KN/m ³
11	cohesion (c)	882.59 KN/m ²
12	friction angle (φ)	12 ⁰
13	Permeability	41.09 x10 ⁻² mm/sec

3.2 Hydrated Lime: Lime is a calcium containing inorganic material in which carbonates, oxides and hydroxides predominate. It is also name of the natural mineral $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. Molecular weight of calcium hydroxide 74.09g mol. Which occurs as a product of coal seam fires and in altered limestone Xenoliths volcanic ejection. The lime was bought in Dutta Scientific Laboratory and its company name is ISOCHEM 1016.

Table 2: Chemical property of hydrated lime

1	Chemical name	Hydrated lime
2	Physical appearance	Dry white powder
3	Primary constituents	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$
4	Specific gravity	2.3
5	Bulk density KN/ m3	7.85
6	CaO	>82.2
7	MgO	<0.49
8	Fe_2O_3	<2.1

3.3 Coir Fiber: Coir fibre, derived from the outer husk of coconuts, has gained attention in geotechnical engineering due to its unique properties that can be beneficial in various construction applications. Coconut coir fibre is extracted from outer shell of a coconut.

Table 3: Physical Property of Coir Fibre

SL NO	Physical Property	Particulars
1	Length	140-190 mm
2	Diameter	0.1-1.5 mm
Moisture Absorption Capacity		
3	Treated RDCF	29.62%
4	Untreated RDCF	46.67%

IV. Result

4.1 Optimization of lime in CRP Soil

Fig 1: Variation of strength of CRP soil treated with the varying percentage of lime

From the Fig 1 it has been observed that addition of varying percentage of lime to CRP soil strength increases up to CRP soil stabilized with 2% lime beyond that strength reduces. The increase in strength up to 2% lime is due to formation of cluster and with curing further strength increases this is due to the disintegration of cluster with curing because of formation of C-S-H gel product. However, beyond 2% lime strength reduces due to disintegration of cluster for immediate sample and also due to load of conformity with increase in lime content strength reduces of soil in Fig 1.

4.2 Performance of lime treated CRP soil in untreated and NaCl treated RDCF.

Fig 2: Variation of Triaxial shear strength of soil treated with lime and fiber

From Fig 2 it has been observed that addition of lime with coir fiber curing densification of cluster lead to increase in strength for all curing periods. From Fig 2 it has been observed that addition of RDCF further enhances its strength performance. This is because fiber surface generates passive resistance against sliding of particles hence sliding resistance between particles increases. Hence Triaxial Shear strength increases in presence of untreated RDCF coir fiber.

Fig 3: Variation of strength of CRP soil with different soil matrix for 0th Day Test

Fig 4: Variation of strength of CRP soil with different soil matrix for 7th Day Test

Fig 5: Variation of strength of CRP soil with different soil matrix for 30th Day Test

From Fig 3-5 it has been observed that soil alone shows lower strength carrying capacity with ductility behavior after post peak failure, whereas soil stabilized with optimum lime no doubt that there will be a maximum improvement in all curing period which had shown, however after post peak failure behavior will be brittle in nature, whereas addition of treated and untreated fiber to the lime stabilized CRP soil not only improves the strength but also the failure behavior (post peak) shows its ductility behavior which is very much important for civil engineering field.

V. Conclusion

Based on experimental result following conclusions were drawn:

1. CRP soil treated with 2% lime improves the strength by 51.2%.
2. Addition of 0.5% RDCF both concentrated and treated improves durability behavior of soil matrix.
3. Addition of NaCl treated fiber to lime treated soil strength improves and it is higher than all other concentrations.
4. Addition of lime reduces K-value.
5. Addition of fiber to lime treated soil marginally increases the K value.

Reference

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Notations

Ca (OH)₂ Calcium Hydroxide (Hydrated Lime)

CRP Soil=ChannaRayaPatna Soil

MDD= Maximum Dry Density

OMC= Optimum Moisture Content

RDCF= Randomly Distributed Coir Fiber